

MOISTURE-INDUCED SWELLING PROPERTIES OF NATURAL CELLULOSE FIBRES CHARACTERIZED BY SYNCHROTRON X-RAY COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

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Keywords: Wood fibre, X-ray microtomography, Finite element method, Hygroexpansion

ABSTRACT

Natural cellulose fibres have the advantage of being renewable, generally low cost and having high specific mechanical properties. A major drawback, particularly for outdoor applications, is the tendency of cellulose fibres to take up water and swell. In development of dimensionally stable cellulose fibres, it is of interest to characterize the hygroexpansion coefficient, e.g. in terms of swelling strains per change in surrounding relative humidity, of fibres in equilibrium conditions. This effect can be indirectly measured by swelling of macroscopic samples. Direct swelling measurements on individual fibres is not straightforward due to the minute and relatively irregular dimensions of the natural fibres and scatter induced by variability in the microfibril angle. Synchrotron X-ray micro-computed tomography (X μ CT) is making it possible to measure three-dimensional geometries at sub-micron resolution. We here present results from X μ CT assisted characterization of the geometrical changes of a single never-dried earlywood Norway spruce tracheid. The three-dimensional images were segmented, meshed and used in finite-element simulations. The cell-wall hygroexpansion coefficients of the predominating S2 layer was identified by a finite-element updating scheme, where the measured geometry of the unconstrained fibre in a dry state (47% relative humidity) and a wet state (80% relative humidity) was compared with the predicted geometry. The numerical model accounted for the detailed geometry of the fibre, the microfibril angle, the moisture dependent stiffness in a large-deformation framework. The identified values were 0.17 strain per change in relative humidity transverse to the microfibrils, and 0.014 in the microfibril direction. These values could in principle be regarded as material properties since the structural effects of the fibre are incorporated in the finite-element model.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellulose fibres from natural resources are constantly gaining increased interest in composite applications, as an alternative to non-renewable reinforcements. A major drawback of cellulose fibres is that they are hygroscopic compared with most synthetic fibres. They tend to take up moisture and swell in the presence of water. In addition to dimensional instability the mechanics properties of the fibres are adversely affected by the presence of moisture. Micromechanical models can be useful to relate swelling of the constituents to that of the composite material. Essentially, micromechanics can thus be used in predicted and controlling moisture-induced dimensional instability. Such models rely, however, on the input parameters. Since the swelling of the fibres is the main contributor to the swelling of the composites for materials based on cellulose natural fibres, the swelling properties of the natural fibre is a key property, which should be given with a sufficient degree of accuracy. Cellulose fibres for composite applications are typically from agricultural crops or from wood. Annual crops like hemp or flax show high degree of orientation and a high content of ordered cellulose, whereas wood give shorter fibres with a lower degree of crystalline cellulose. Processing of wood fibres is facilitated by large scale infrastructure in pulp and paper mills, meaning that wood fibres can

be manufactured at relatively low cost [1]. In this work, focus is placed on wood fibres, and more specifically Norway spruce, which is a prevalent species in forestry in the northern hemisphere. The main building block of wood fibres is the S2 cell-wall layer. The moisture swelling properties of the cell wall of wood fibres is not very well investigated experimentally. This work focuses on in-situ measurement of these properties using X-ray micro computed tomography (X μ CT). The starting point is the pristine native wood fibre, i.e. a never-dried earlywood tracheid from the stem in the green state. Drying, pulping, chemical treatment etc. will surely affect the swelling properties, but the unprocessed starting fibre is ideally always the same. Three-dimensional images obtained by X μ CT, taken intermittently as the moisture content is varied, were used as input in a mixed numerical-experimental method to identify the cell-wall swelling properties. These images were segmented by well-defined surfaces to quantify the fibre geometries. A linear hygroelastic model including the dominant S2 cell-wall layer was used in finite element simulations with the measured fibre geometries. The anisotropic moisture-dependent elastic properties of this layer were predicted by homogenisation of the cell-wall constituents. The only fitting parameters were the longitudinal and transverse hygroexpansion coefficients of the cell-wall layer. These parameters were identified by minimising the difference between simulated and predicted fibre deformation after moderate absorption. The constitute model accounting for finite deformation was chosen since the measured strains were found to be large.

The interested reader will find more information on this study in a manuscript included in the recent PhD thesis of Thomas Joffre [2], which is concurrently considered for publication in a scientific journal. The present conference paper is a shortened and rewritten version, and should only be regarded as a written accompanying support to the oral presentation to be given at ICCM20.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 X-ray micro computed tomography

Wet earlywood tracheids from Norway spruce (*Picea Abies*) were extracted from the wood stem using thin tweezers. The fibres were kept in the wet state. Since beam time was limited, only one fibre was characterized in the synchrotron. The scans were made at 47% relative humidity (RH), corresponding to the ambient state (dry state), and at 80% RH referred to as the wet state. The humidity was maintained by a slow flow of air at designated level of relative humidity inside a plastic pipe, where the fibre was contained. During scanning and at equilibrium conditions, the protective pipe was sealed to keep the fibre stable. Sorption tests were carried out from equilibrium conditions at 47% RH to 80% RH. Although the moisture content of the cell wall would be a better physical description, the ambient relative humidity to describe the moisture state of the fibre since the weight of the fibre is too low to be measured accurately with equipment available to us. The sorption curves are known to non-linear for wood materials [3]. For small changes in moisture contents in the straight part of the sorption isotherm curve far away from the saturation point, the moisture content-relative humidity relation can, however, be regarded as linear. Furthermore, although sorption/desorption hysteresis is an inherent property of wood [4], only the absorption is considered here, which is of engineering relevance of dimensional instability caused by swelling of wood during moisture uptake.

The three-dimensional grey-scale voxel images were obtained from 1500 radiographs over 180 degrees of the single wood cell at two levels of relative humidity on the beamline ID19 of the ESRF (Grenoble, France). The fibre was irradiated by an X-ray monochromatic beam light with an energy level of 17.6 keV, and $\Delta E/E = 2 \times 10^{-5}$) The transmitted light was converted into visible light using a GGG scintillator and recorded using the FReLoN camera at ESRF. A pixel size of 0.35 μ m was achieved in the projected two-dimensional images. The three-dimensional images were reconstructed using a filter-back projection algorithm (Harauz and van Heel, 1986). To smooth and partly remove the background noise of the images, the images were processed with Gaussian filter and subsequently manually thresholded. To make meshing easier, the edges of the images were then manually smoothed from protruding parts. The details of the finite element model and the constitutive model can be found in Ref. 2.

2.2 Microfibril angle measurement

The obliquely oriented anisotropy of the cell wall is given by the direction of the microfibrils in the cell wall. This value is a necessary input to the finite element simulations. The microfibrils within the cell wall are highly crystalline and aligned in the different layers, S1, S2 and S3. Since the S2 layer is dominating, the influence of the other two layers are neglected, both in the determination of the microfibril angle (MFA), and in the mechanical model. The extremity of the tested fibre was carefully sectioned longitudinally with a thin razor blade. Then the fiber was rotated between two cross polarizing filters to find the angle where no light is able to go through the cell wall, at the maximum extinction position. The average MFA of the cell wall correspond to the angle between the fibre axis and the maximum extinction position.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The three dimensional images obtained by X μ CT were analyzed with respect to the twist angle along the fibre from common point of reference, cf. Fig. 1(a). The same fibre was studied at different levels of relative humidity. Along the fibre, two-dimensional cross sections were obtained at regular intervals. By image analysis, the major and minor axes of the somewhat flatted fibres were determined, as shown schematically in Fig. 1(b). The twist angle as a function of position and relative humidity is plotted in Fig. 1(a). It can be seen that the fibre became more twisted for lower levels of relative humidity. The fibre is believed to be straight and untwisted in the saturated green state. Only the two higher levels of relative humidity were used in the comparisons with finite element simulations. At 20% relative humidity irreversible changes on the supramolecular level are expected in the drying process, e.g. fibril aggregation.

Figure 1: (a) Twist angle along a single wood fibre as a function of surrounding relative humidity with least-square fitted trend lines. (b) Definition of twist angle of in the fibre cross section.

The constitutive hygroelastic model including finite deformation is presented in detail in Ref. 2. Essentially, the fitting parameters are the hygroexpansion coefficients of the unidirectional transversely isotropic cell wall, namely β_L and β_T , given in units of strain per change in ambient relative humidity. The softening effects of moisture on the elastic properties are necessarily taken into consideration by a micromechanical model [5], based on measured softening of the constituent cell-wall polymers. The principles of the parameter identification procedure are summarized in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Inverse modeling using a mixed experimental-numerical approach to identify the hygroexpansion coefficients of the transversely isotropic cell wall material.

Using the finite element updating technique it was possible to identify the hygroexpansion coefficient of the studied wood fibre by minimizing the difference in twist angle between the experimental results and the simulations. The values are presented in Table 1 together with estimates from other methods reported in the literature. The estimated value for the dominant transverse hygroexpansion coefficient falls in the lower range of values obtained in other investigations, ~ 0.1 - 0.4 , e.g from sorption tests of composites [6], paper [9], and wood [10] or measurement on embedded pulp fibres by means of X-ray microtomography [7]. However, it should be emphasised that the hygroexpansion is measured in the fibril direction (fibres with an MFA determined to be 15°), whereas the other studies deals with an average of the swelling of different fibres having different geometries as well as different MFAs. In pulp fibres, the ultrastructure of the cell wall is modified. The mobility of the polymer chains within the cell wall is typically restrained, which will necessarily affect the swelling behaviour. The micromechanical models used in the back-calculated values in Table 1 are based on different assumptions. The present assumptions are considered to be more realistic than those made in the other studies. Especially, (i) the detailed geometry of the fibres are taken into account, (ii) large deformations and rotations are considered, (iii) the transverse and longitudinal hygroexpansion coefficients are identified independently, and (iv) the influence of moisture on the elastic properties of the cell wall is accounted for.

Method	β_L (ϵ/RH)	β_T (ϵ/RH)
Identified from X- μ CT and FE simulation (green state), this study	0.014	0.17
Back calculated from composite properties (pulp fibers) [6]	-	0.28
Measured from X- μ CT images (pulp fibers) [7]	-	0.2
Measured from X- μ CT images (wood) [8]	-	0.22
Estimated from paper sample [9]	-	0.17
Estimated from wood samples [10]	-	0.21
Estimated from FE simulation [11]	-	0.13
Analytical modelling based from input obtained by molecular dynamic simulation of the cell-wall polymers [12]	0.02	0.44

Table 1: Hygroexpansion coefficient of wood cell walls from the present study and literature.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A never-dried cellulose wood fibre was scanned in synchrotron X-ray micro-computed tomography under equilibrium conditions at two different levels of relative humidity. The obtained images have been used as input in three-dimensional finite-element simulations. A mixed numerical-experimental method has then been used to identify the hygroelastic deformation of the wood fibre such that the numerical simulation matches the experimental results in terms of the twist angle. Using this mixed method it was possible to estimate the hygroexpansion coefficients despite the anisotropic irregular structure, having a cross section no more than 40 μm . The fitted values were 0.014 strain per change in relative humidity in the microfibril direction of the cell wall, and 0.17 in the transverse direction. Although the swelling of wood fibres depends on external parameters such as the microfibril angle and the geometry of the fibre, the measured hygroexpansion coefficients in this study could be regarded as a material properties and thus can be used as input of micromechanical models aiming to predict the hygroelastic behaviour of various wood-fibre based engineering materials.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Financial mobility support to carry out the experiments from EU COST Action FP0802 (Experimental and Computational Micro-Characterization Techniques in Wood Mechanics) is gratefully acknowledged. The authors would also like to gratefully acknowledge the ESRF (beamline ID19) where the microtomography experiments were performed in the framework of the Long Term Project “ma127: Heterogeneous Fibrous Materials”. This research was made possible at LGP2 thanks to the facilities of the TekLiCell platform funded by the Région Rhône-Alpes (ERDF: European Regional Development Fund). LGP2 and 3SR laboratories are parts of the LabEx Tec 21 (Investissements d’Avenir - grant agreement n°ANR-11-LABX-0030) and of the Énergies du Futur and PolyNat Carnot Institutes (Investissements d’Avenir - grant agreements n°ANR-11-CARN-007-01 and ANR-11-CARN-030-01).

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